

INNOVATIVE PROCESSES AND EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING

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Abstract: *With the current trend of globalization and close interaction of different languages and cultures, a foreign language has taken on a new significance, as many individuals find themselves in situations where they must communicate or conduct business in a foreign language. As a result, the demand to learn a foreign language is expanding, as is interest in teaching methods for this topic. In this context, the question of implementing new techniques and methodologies in the field of foreign language instruction was particularly pressing.*

Key words: *innovation process, trend of globalization, implementing the course, new knowledge skills, development of an educational institution, design and organize the process of school development, innovative educational technologies, to analyze the experience and results of innovative activities.*

Introduction. Addressing the problems of innovation and highlighting them among the most important areas of modern scientific thought was the result of awareness of the growing dynamics of innovation processes in society. The development of scientific interests in this direction revealed the complexity and multidimensionality of this phenomenon, which led to the emergence of various approaches to its analysis. In pedagogical science today there are theoretical and practical prerequisites that are most appropriate to take into account when implementing the course “Innovative processes in education”. Firstly, the need to train specialists in the development and implementation of innovative educational technologies of various types and levels. The purpose of mastering discipline. Secondly, it is the domestic and foreign psychological and pedagogical science of relevant developments and their approbation in the field of pedagogical innovations. (M.V. Clarin, V.Ya. Lyaudis, L.S. Podymova, V.A. Khutorskoy, R.N. Yusufbekova and others).

N.E. Stenyakova analyzes “Innovative processes in education” and consists in mastering the competencies of active transformative activity by students, designing and organizing the development process, determining the criteria for the effectiveness of the development of an educational institution, as well as familiarizing students with modern innovative processes in education, which are the driving force behind the modernization of the education system. Constructive activity, in turn, is divided into structural and substantive: selection and composition of educational material, planning and construction of the pedagogical process, structural and operational planning of actions and activities of students and constructive and material design of educational tools of the pedagogical process. Organizing activities involve the implementation of a system of actions aimed at involving students in various activities, creating a team and organizing joint events [1,2,3].

Materials and methods. Communicative activity is aimed at establishing pedagogically acceptable teacher relationships with students, other school teachers, the public and parents. However, these components, on the one hand, can equally be attributed not only to teaching, but also to almost any other activity, and on the other hand, they do not sufficiently disclose all aspects and directions of teaching in detail [4-9].

A. Shcherbakov connects constructive, organizational and research components that manifest themselves in any activity. But this concretizes the teacher's function at the stage of the educational process, providing organizational components of pedagogical activity as a unity of informational, developmental and mobilization functions. Special attention should be paid to the research function. The implementation of the research function requires the teacher to have a scientific approach to educational phenomena, skills in using heuristic search methods and scientific and pedagogical research, including the analysis of his own experience and the experience of other teachers [10-17]. The structural components of pedagogical activity can be represented as internally related analytical, predictive and projective functions. The structural components of pedagogical activity can be represented as internal interrelated analytical, predictive and projective functions. In-depth study of the content of the communicative function allows us to define it as a cross-cutting perceptual, actually communicative and communicative-operational function. The perceptual function is associated with penetration into the inner world of a person, in fact, the communicative one is aimed at establishing pedagogically appropriate relationships and the operational one involves the active use of educational technologies. [18-23]. The effectiveness of the educational process is due to the presence of constant feedback. This allows the teacher to receive timely information about the results obtained in accordance with the schedule of tasks. For this reason, it is necessary to allocate an evaluation component in the structure of pedagogical activity. All components or functional types of activity that are manifested in a teacher of any specialty. Their implementation implies the teacher's possession of special skills [24-28]. The teacher is a subject of pedagogical activity, one of the most important requirements that the teaching profession imposes is the definition of the social and professional status of its representatives. The teacher expresses himself as a subject of pedagogical activity. The teacher's position is a system of intellectual, volitional and emotional-evaluative attitude to the world, pedagogical reality and educational activities in particular, which are the source of his activity. This is determined, on the one hand, by the requirements and features that society presents and provides to him. On the other hand, these are internal, private sources of activity - the drives, feelings, motives and goals of the teacher, his values, worldview, ideals. [29-31]. The teacher's position shows his identity, the nature of social orientation, the type of civic behavior and activity. The social position of a teacher grows out of belief systems and values that were formed in high school. In the process of learning on their basis, a motivational and value attitude to the teacher's profession, goals and means of teaching is formed. The motivation associated with educational activity in the broadest sense of the word will ultimately be expressed in the concentration that underlies the personality of the teacher. [38-44]. The position of a social pedagogue largely determines his professional position. . However, there was no direct connection here, because education is always based on personal interaction. That is why the teacher, clearly realizing that he does not always give a detailed answer, why he acts this way and not otherwise. Recruitment of professionals in accordance with the requirements of the teacher is defined as professional commitment to teaching. It includes the correct allocation, on the one hand, of psychological and physical readiness, and on the other - scientific, theoretical and practical training as the basis of professionalism. [37-41]. V.A. Krutetsky highlights teaching, academic, communication skills, as well as the imagination of the teacher and the ability to distribute focus.

A *teacher* is not just a profession that translates knowledge and the creation of a high human mission, the affirmation of a human personality. In this regard, the goal of pedagogical education can be presented as the continuous general and professional development of a new type of teacher, which is characterized by: > high responsibility and social activity; > love for

children, need and ability to give them the soul; ➤ true intelligence, spiritual culture, desire and ability to work with others; ➤ professionalism, innovative style of scientific and pedagogical thinking, readiness to create new values and creative decision-making; ➤ the need for constant self-education and readiness for it; ➤ physical and mental health, professional performance. The work of a teacher based on ideological beliefs determines all other properties and characteristics of a person expressing his social and moral orientation. In particular, social needs and moral values, a sense of public duty and civic responsibility. Ideological beliefs are the basis of the teacher's social activity. [45-49]. That is why it is considered the most profound fundamental characteristic of a teacher's personality. The teacher is a citizen devoted to his people close to him. This is not limited to a narrow circle of his personal problems, his life is constantly connected with village life, the city where he lives and works. In the structure of the teacher's personality, a special role belongs to the professional and pedagogical orientation. This is the skeleton around which the main professionally significant properties of the teacher's personality are collected.

Results and discussion. The professional orientation of the teacher's personality includes interest in the teaching profession, pedagogical vocation, professional and pedagogical intentions and inclinations. The basis of pedagogical orientation is an interest in the teaching profession, which is reflected in a positive emotional attitude towards children, parents, educational activities in general and its specific features in an effort to master pedagogical knowledge and skills. Pedagogical vocation, in contrast to pedagogical interest, which may be a tendency to contemplation, grows out of awareness of the ability to pedagogical work. The basis of the pedagogical vocation is love for children. This fundamental quality is a prerequisite for self-improvement, self-development of many significant qualities that characterize the professional and pedagogical orientation of teachers. Among these qualities is teaching duty and responsibility. Driven by a sense of pedagogical duty, the teacher is always in a hurry to help children and adults, all those who need it, within their rights. He is demanding of himself, scrupulously following the original code of moral teaching. The highest manifestation of pedagogical duty is the dedication of teachers. That it is an expression of motivation and value attitude to work. A teacher should have such high-quality work, regardless of the time, sometimes even in a serious state of health. A vivid example of professional dedication to the life and work of A.S. Makarenko and V.A. Sukhomlinsky. An exceptional example of dedication and self-sacrifice is the life and feat of Janusz Korczak, an outstanding Polish doctor and teacher who despised the Nazis who offered to stay alive and went to the crematorium furnace with his students. The teacher's relationships with colleagues, parents and children, based on the awareness of professional duty and a sense of responsibility, constitute the essence of pedagogical tact, which is both a sense of proportion and a conscious dosage of actions and the ability to control it and, if necessary, balance it in one way or another. The tactics of the teacher's behavior in any case consists in anticipating its consequences, choosing the appropriate style and tone, time and place of the pedagogical action, as well as making timely adjustments. The teaching cycle largely depends on the personal qualities of the teacher, his worldview, culture, faith, civic and professional skills. This is the foundation on which trusting relationships between teachers and students grow. Pedagogical tact is especially clearly manifested in the control and evaluation by the teacher, for whom special care and fairness are extremely important. Educational justice is a kind of indicator of the objectivity of the teacher, the level of his moral education. V.A. Sukhomlinsky wrote: "Justice is the basis of trust in a child. But there is some kind of abstract justice - these are individual or personal interests, passions, impulses, in order to be fair, it is necessary to know the subtleties of the spiritual world of each child." Personality

qualities that characterize the professional and pedagogical orientation of a teacher are a necessary condition and a concentrated expression of his authority. If the usual expressions "scientific authority", "recognized authority in their field" sound in other professions, then the teacher can be a single and indivisible authority of the individual. The cognitive orientation of the personality is based on the components of spiritual needs and interests. One of the manifestations of spiritual forces and cultural needs is the need for knowledge. For the continuity of pedagogical actions should be a necessary condition for professional development and improvement. One of the main factors of cognitive interest is love for the subject being taught. Tolstoy remarked that "if you want science to educate a student, to awaken a love for science, you must love them and know that students will love you and you will educate them, but if you don't love them, it doesn't matter that all efforts will be in vain, there will be no educational impacts" . He believed that "the masters of teaching know the ABC of their science so well that in the classroom, in the process of studying the material, the focus of his attention is not the actual content of what is being studied, but the students, their mental work, their thinking, the difficulties of mental work."

Conclusion. Currently, the interactive method plays an important role in teaching, due to the fact that this method is one of the most interesting and motivating for schoolchildren and female students. Thus, the method includes several features. The first feature of this method is that teachers often use innovative technologies, and this attracts students to study hard. This feature attracts students to study, due to the fact that we live in the era of technology and our younger generation is interested in them. The second feature is the games that are used during the lesson, they motivate students to study. However, despite these features, the teacher who uses this method must have several features. The teacher must have a good level of knowledge, understandable and, of course, very flexible. Flexibility is the main feature of teaching, it helps to properly organize the lesson, rally the whole class and motivate them to study hard. One aspect that I find flexible is the teacher's enthusiasm, skills and positive mood in the classroom. We all have our favorite teachers who have had a huge impact on our lives with their creativity, tolerance and individual approach to students.

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